
IOP | Institute of Physics

Environmental Physics Group

NEWSLETTER

November 2007

Winners of the 2006 Essay Competition were presented with their prizes at the Members' Day meeting in May. From left: Felix Palmer (joint first prize), Bethan White (third prize) and Chris Holt (joint first prize).

<http://institute-of-physics.org/activity/groups/subject/env/index.html>

Contents

Contents.....	2
News	2
EPG Essay Competition 2007.....	2
Special Message to Students / Early Career Physicists	3
Windscale Fire 50 th anniversary	3
Reports from previous events.....	6
EPG Members' Meeting and London/SE Branch Lecture (2nd May)	6
Discovery, Environmental Physics and the Scottish Branch AGM (2 nd June)	8
Heated global warming debate at 76 Portland Place (7 th June).....	9
50 Years of Hartland Observatory (9 th -10 th June)	10
Climate Change 2007: The Physical Basis (13 th June).....	11
Optical Environmental Sensing V (17th October)	12
Forthcoming Events	14
Severe Weather - Origins and Prediction (Organised jointly with the South Central Group).....	14
Environmental Physics Group Members' Meeting: First announcement and call for presentations.....	14
Physics of Ice: First announcement	15
EPG Committee	16
Committee Statistics.....	18

News

EPG Essay Competition 2007

Entries are now invited for this year's EPG Essay Competition. The aim of the competition is to encourage and recognise excellence in communicating the significance, value and rewarding nature of engaging with environmental physics. Entries should cover any aspect encompassed by the Group's interests in environmental physics, which include, but are not limited to: atmosphere and climate; hydrology; plant physics; glaciology; waste; energy; the built environment.

- a cash prize and certificate will be awarded to the winning author(s);
- the winning entry will also be considered for publication (last year's winners have been published in Physics Education);
- the competition is open to all, but entries from students are particularly welcome;
- essays must be no more than 2,000 words long;
- the closing date is 31st December 2007.

Entries must be original and will be judged on writing quality and content. Essays adopting a purely scientific, policy-related or some other perspective will be welcomed. It is hoped that presentations will be made to and by the winning author(s) at the Group's Members' meeting in May 2008.

Entries should be sent to: env.essay@physics.org, preferably as a pdf file, along with full contact details and student status if appropriate. Entries may be also be submitted by post to:

The Chair, Environmental Physics Group, c/o The Institute of Physics,
76 Portland Place, London, W1B 1NT

Further details are available on the Group's web site or from env.essay@physics.org.

Special Message to Students / Early Career Physicists

A special session of the forthcoming AGM will be dedicated to presentations from students and early career physicists (those who have been in paid employment for <10 years) to encourage greater involvement within the group. The purpose of this event is to promote greater engagement, discussion and integration between students and early career physicists. It is also the ideal situation to meet other like-minded physicists passionate about the environment. The event also provides a unique opportunity for students and early career physicists to present their work, whether it is a piece of coursework, dissertation or research. Environmental physics encapsulates a wide field, and there will be plenty of opportunity for discussion in an informal and friendly setting.

Whether you are a student, or someone who has several years of research experience, and if you would like an opportunity to present your work, please contact Sally Brown (sb20@soton.ac.uk).

A number of *EPG travel bursaries* will be allocated to this meeting to assist with travel costs. If you are interested in attending, please could you register your interest by emailing Sally Brown in the email address above. Please also see more details of the AGM in the "forthcoming events" section later in this Newsletter.

Windscale Fire 50th anniversary

The 50th anniversary of a major fire at the Windscale military reactor (known as No. 1 Pile), on 10th October 1957, which was then the world's worst nuclear disaster, has attracted substantial media coverage.

Dr John Garland, a member of the EPG committee and a former researcher at UKAEA, recently published a paper in the journal *Atmospheric Environment* in which he showed that contemporary researchers underestimated the radioactivity emitted. Garland and Wakeford expect about 240 cancers to occur as a consequence of the fire compared to the 200 previously expected. This article was covered in BBC News Online. The full reference is:

J.A. Garland and R. Wakeford, Atmospheric emissions from the Windscale accident of October 1957 *Atmospheric Environment*, **41**, 18, pp 3904-3920 (2007)
BBC News Online article <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/science/nature/7030536.stm>

On the day of the anniversary of the fire, an hour long documentary was shown on BBC2. The build up to nuclear power in the UK was motivated by the need to obtain plutonium, and later, deuterium, for nuclear bombs was described in detail. This rather more sinister motivation for nuclear physics than the provision of cheap electrical power for the masses is perhaps not always made clear to those of us who have grown up in the nuclear era, from my own memory of school trips to nuclear power stations. Perhaps understandably, the original reasons to develop nuclear technology are rarely remembered in contemporary discussions about the role of nuclear power in combating climate change, and for this reason the documentary was a topical and interesting program.

Radiation measurements at Windscale (from guardian.co.uk)

The documentary benefited hugely from the first-hand accounts of several members of Windscale staff who were working at the site during the incident in 1957, many of whom are now in their eighties. Particularly compelling was the description of the fire and the attempts to extinguish it, as recalled by the then deputy general manager, Tom Tuohy. The fire began in the nuclear pile during a so-called "Wigner release" which aimed to redistribute the excess energy in the graphite lattice, produced as a result of its bombardment by neutrons. If the pile was heated by operators, this initiated a controlled and spatially uniform release of the potential energy stored in the lattice. However on this occasion the

temperature readings were anomalous, and the radioactivity monitors high in

the chimneys saturated, then slowly decreased, indicating that radioactive material had been blown upwards out of the pile by the large fans that were used to cool it. At this point the staff at the reactor realised there was a problem, and on inspection it became clear that the uranium fuel was red hot. Various attempts were made to extinguish the fire, for instance by pushing the burning fuel rods out of the reactor with scaffolding poles. This was not a success and neither was an attempt to use carbon dioxide. Eventually Tuohy obtained special permission to use water to put out the blaze. He knew this was very risky since it could cause an explosion, but, in the event, it also did not put out the fire. Tuohy then realised that the air flow from the “cooling” fans was actually contributing to the development of the fire and ordered them to be switched off – at which point the fire quietly died away. The aftermath and Inquiry was reported in the documentary, which implied that the official explanation of human error was incomplete and that mistakes made could well have been due to design faults arising from the need to deliver fuel for nuclear weapons under time pressure.

The programme was unhelpfully vague in its use of the word “explosion”. On one hand it used the word to describe a nuclear explosion in the physical sense (as in a nuclear bomb), but also used “explosion” to describe any event resulting from a build up of pressure in a confined space. For instance, the possibility of an explosion following the use of water on the burning reactor was presented as a disastrous outcome that would have hugely risked the nearby population. Whilst such an explosion would, no doubt, have distributed radioactive material widely, a nuclear explosion – which was probably not what was meant - would have been appallingly worse. Whether this was an inaccuracy or an ambiguity is impossible to know: it certainly served to make the story as exciting as possible.

This was a well-researched documentary that made use of the relatively recently released archive sources, such as recordings of the interviews from the subsequent enquiry led by Sir William Penney, in addition to the first-hand accounts. It was certainly gripping viewing.

Karen Aplin (Rutherford Appleton Laboratory)

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IOP Institute of Physics**Reports from previous events****EPG Members' Meeting and London/SE Branch Lecture (2nd May)**

The 4th Members' Meeting was held on Wednesday 2 May in the Phillips Room at 76 Portland Place. The format differed from previous meetings, starting at 3.30 pm with tea and continuing into the evening with a buffet supper at 8 pm.

The formal business started with three presentations of different aspects of environmental physics. Dr Kathy Maskell of the Walker Institute, Reading University, spoke on *Climate change - is it really happening?* She pointed out that atmospheric CO₂ levels were the highest for 650,000 years and the current solar forcing of 0.12Wm⁻² was vastly outweighed by anthropogenic forcing of 1.6Wm⁻². There was a good match with observations of rising global temperature only if the human influence was included and by 2100 the earth would be 2–4K warmer on average and sea levels would rise by 0.2–0.6m. There would be different effects on temperature and precipitation in different locations so there was a need for higher-resolution models to estimate local variations and plan effective mitigation measures.

Ivan Haigh of Southampton University discussed *Sea level trends in the English Channel over the 20th century* noting that, although data from tide gauges suggest that sea level has risen by $1\text{--}2\text{mmyr}^{-1}$ over the past 200 years, recent satellite measurements show that the rate is now 3mmyr^{-1} and rising, exacerbated on the south coast by isostatic sinking of 0.5mmyr^{-1} . Observed sea level rise is the sum of the mean sea level, tidal movement, and surges due to weather. Observations from 15 sites with at least 35 years of data suggest that, contrary to popular belief, there has been no increase in the size of storm surges, but a slightly higher rise in mean high water (2.18mmyr^{-1}) than mean low water (2.08mmyr^{-1}) so that the mean tidal range is also increasing. Overall, mean sea level is predicted to rise between 18 and 59 cm between 1990 and 2090, coupled with a sinking of the land by 11 cm, a net change of from 29 to 70 cm.

The third presentation was by Dr James McLauchlin of University College Dublin on *Passive measurements of Thoron and its progeny in some dwellings in Ireland*. Although the average dose in Ireland, 3.6mSvyr^{-1} , is comparable with that in the UK (2.7mSvyr^{-1}), areas of Karstic limestone have much higher levels as a result of the redeposition of leached salts. In addition, although both radon (^{222}Ra) and thoron (^{220}Ra) emit high-energy α -particles, radon has a long half-life and 9 short-lived decay products whereas thoron has a short-half life (and is therefore unaffected by ventilation) but 40 long-lived products: on average, 97% of a dose of thoron is concentrated in the lungs where it can trigger tumours. Dr McLauchlin recalled one house with a radiation level of $54,000\text{Bqm}^{-3}$ in which the occupant, though never a smoker, died from lung cancer. He described measurement techniques that discriminated between radon and thoron, as well as assessing the combined dose, and methods of house construction that would minimise the entry of thoron in susceptible locations.

The three prize-winners of the 2006 essay competition, detailed in the Spring 2007 Newsletter, then gave short summaries of their topics and received their winners' cheques and commemorative certificates from the IoP. Joint first-prize winners, Chris Holt, a retired member, spoke on *Energy from the oceans* and Felix Palmer, a second-year undergraduate from Oxford University, on *Physics – saviour of the planet*. Third-prize winner Bethan White, a third-year student from Bristol University, discussed *Physics in the current climate*, a succinct overview of the current status of global climate modelling.

After a short AGM, the group squeezed into a packed hall with the London and South-East Branch at 6.30 pm for the evening lecture on *Rainbows, Haloes and Glories* from Prof. Alan Davies of the University of Hertfordshire. Illustrated by many wonderfully evocative pictures of these atmospheric optical phenomena, Prof. Davies recounted the history of the theories of the rainbow from Aristotle through Roger Bacon (1266) to Newton, Descartes and the present, and described the necessary conditions for the various phenomena to be visible. At

the end of one hour, questions came thick and fast and a vigorous discussion from the floor ensued: at 8 pm the chairman eventually called a halt to the proceedings which were not just entertaining and informative, but also entrancing. Derek Rose (Newcastle University)

Discovery, Environmental Physics and the Scottish Branch AGM (2nd June)

The Institute of Physics in Scotland held a day of talks about environmental physics, followed by the AGM and dinner on 2 June 2007. The day was held at Discovery Point in Dundee. This was an excellent venue with an exhibition about Antarctica and Royal Research Ship (RRS) Discovery there to entertain those not so interested in environmental physics. Prof. Cracknell, recently retired from the University of Dundee, started with a talk on *Fossil fuels, global warming and the threat to our way of life*. He took us skillfully through the evidence behind climate change and the dangers it presents to the current way we live our lives. Dr Mhairi Coyle of the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, provided more detail on one greenhouse gas with her talk entitled *Tropospheric Ozone – pollutant and greenhouse gas*. Lunch was followed by another excellent presentation on *the physics of marine remote sensing*. Dr Alex Cunningham of the University of Strathclyde outlined the work he is doing in monitoring and modelling algal blooms. Dr Paul Williams of the IOP Environmental Physics group finished off the environmental part of the day with a passionate lecture on *Climate Change and the Gulf Stream*. The main thrust of the discussion centred round the chances of the Gulf Stream slowing down and what affects this might have on the climate of the UK.

Those who did not need to be involved in the Branch AGM were invited to a special showing of the “Magic Planet” at Sensation, Dundee’s Science Centre. In the meantime, the AGM was efficiently dealt with so that we could all enjoy a tour on RRS Discovery. The ship was built in Dundee and was used by Captain Scott on a remarkable Antarctic expedition from 1902 to 1904. The ship was built especially for research purposes and, as physicists, we were especially interested in the experiments of the ship’s physicist, Louis Bernacchi. His work included magnetic measurements, auroral observations and seismic recordings and the results were published by the Royal Geographical Society.

We returned to dry land for dinner and a feast much better than that enjoyed by Scott’s men on the ship. Thanks to the fifty or so people who attended any or all of the talks, AGM or dinner.

Alison Mclure (IoP Scotland)

Heated global warming debate at 76 Portland Place (7th June)

In the same week that the G8 leaders were discussing climate change and agreeing to talk about cutting CO₂ emissions, a large audience packed into the Institute's London centre to hear expert opinion and discussion on the models used to understand climate change. On 7 June, MP and former environment minister Michael Meacher chaired a seminar with prominent speakers from both sides of the climate change debate. Opening the seminar, Meacher said that 10 years ago the issue was hardly on the radar screen; now there were almost daily reports about climate change, including runaway melting of the arctic sea ice, massive methane releases in Siberia and Alaska and dramatic hurricanes. It had been suggested that global warming could create 50 million environmental refugees, while the Pentagon considers climate change to be a greater risk than global terrorism, he said. The argument is that increasing CO₂ levels are responsible for rising global temperatures. The question is whether that is correct.

Though there is an almost universal consensus that the world is warming up, some scientists still question whether CO₂ emissions are causing the change. Prof. Richard Lindzen, an atmospheric scientist from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, is one of them. Addressing the seminar, he discussed the main areas of controversy, which concern the uncertainties in the data, the effect of both negative and positive feedbacks and the sensitivity of the climate to rising CO₂ levels. He went further, however, arguing that the models are fundamentally wrong and do not take sufficient account of the warming in the tropical troposphere rather than at the surface. Based on this, he said, no more than about a third of the Earth's surface warming could be due to the greenhouse effect. It was claimed, he said, that doubling CO₂ should lead to about 1.5°C to 4.5°C warming. However, we were already 86% of the way to a doubling of CO₂ levels but have seen only 0.6-0.8°C warming at the surface, he argued. Lindzen said that each chain in the argument for human-induced global warming was tenuous, leading to an infinitesimally small chance that it was the correct model.

Prof. Alan Thorpe, a distinguished meteorologist and chief executive of the Natural Environment Research Council, presented substantial evidence to support the opposing view. He agreed that there were significant uncertainties in certain aspects of the models, particularly the effects of clouds, but there was no reason to suppose that the models had a systematic bias towards human-induced global warming, he said. He described the close correlation between rising CO₂ levels and global temperatures over the last 100 years. Scientists had created hindcasts to represent the climate during the 20th century as it should have been according to the models, and compared these with actual observations. These showed that the models simulated reality very well, he said. Similarly, predictions had been made since 1990 using the models and these had predicted the state of

the climate during the last 17 years very well, but if anything had underestimated the degree of warming.

(Extracted from an article by Heather Pinnell which appeared in July 2007's issue of Interactions.)

50 Years of Hartland Observatory (9th-10th June)

The Geomagnetic Observatory at Hartland, Devon, held open days on 9th and 10th June 2007 to celebrate the 50th anniversary of the Observatory opening. The British Geological Survey (BGS) provided many exhibits, demonstrations and information in Hartland Village Hall. Dr David Kerridge, Manager of the Seismology and Geomagnetism Programme at BGS gave an introductory evening lecture on the work and history of the Observatory. There were further geophysical exhibits and demonstrations by the Universities of Plymouth and Reading. As well as visitors from far afield, the open days was popular with local people who had long been curious about the scientific activity of the Observatory, readily visible from village footpaths.

Hartland Observatory was built to replace Abinger Observatory in Surrey, where magnetic measurements had been made since 1925. Between them, these two Observatories continued geomagnetic observations which can be traced back to the establishment of the Royal Greenwich Observatory by King Charles II in 1675. Abinger was originally built to replace Greenwich, because electrical noise sources were compromising the measurements there, but development and the associated expansion of electric railways south of London also eventually caused interference with the Abinger measurements too. A new site was sought far from railways, and Hartland in north Devon was chosen.

Many visual displays concerning different geophysical phenomena were made in Hartland Village Hall

Building work at Hartland began in 1955, with the special requirement of non-magnetic construction materials. Any materials with a magnetic content were rejected, and consequently aluminium and copper nails were used. Bricks were individually tested, as some of the bricks had been found to be slightly magnetised by wire brushes used to clean the brick moulds. It is thought that the

incentives given to the builders for finding “failed” (i.e. magnetic) bricks led to some selected bricks being tested – and failing- rather more than once. The work schedule became particularly intense during the 1956 Christmas holidays as, to allow a brief overlap before the final closure of Abinger in April 1957, Hartland had to open on 1st January 1957. (Abinger Observatory remains standing, but it is now a private house, called, succinctly, “The Old Observatory”.)

The Hartland Observatory site consists of five buildings, all aligned North-South, and containing equipment for continuous measurement of the magnetic field. These measurements are widely disseminated and used for navigation and instrument orientation purposes, such as controlling below-ground drilling equipment, which cannot receive Global Positioning System (GPS) signals. A further important use of the Hartland measurements is in constructing the geophysical “aa-index”. This quantity is derived from simultaneous geomagnetic measurements at two approximately antipodal points, currently Hartland and Canberra. The aa-index had been produced continuously since 1868, giving a long reference time series of measured geomagnetic activity. There is also a seismometer at Hartland, which, as well as being sufficiently sensitive to detect some distant global earthquakes, readily detected the magnitude 3.7 Hartland Point earthquake of May 2001.

Artist's impression of geophysicists at work in Abinger Observatory, from a contemporary poster

Giles Harrison (University of Reading) and David Booth (British Geological Survey).

Climate Change 2007: The Physical Basis (13th June)

When Prof. Jonathan Gregory, a lead author of the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) 4th assessment into climate change stated at the beginning of his climate change talk that “climate models do a pretty good job,” it raised many questions. These included why is there so much uncertainty about the future and what will be the impact of our changing climate over the coming century? He went onto explain.

The talk entitled *Climate Change: The Physical Basis* given by Prof. Gregory of Reading University and the Met Office was jointly hosted by the London and

South East Branch of the Institute of Physics. With every seat taken in the lecture room and standing space becoming limited, the audience was eager to hear about the science, new discoveries and the present understanding of the threat of climate change.

To begin answering the question of why there is future climate uncertainty, Jonathan Gregory explained about various parts of the climate system starting with the greenhouse effect. He explained that without the greenhouse effect our earth would be 30°C cooler as radiation would not be trapped within the atmosphere. He progressed with a tour around our earth's systems (and the IPCC 4th assessment report) explaining how glaciers, ice sheets, forests, vegetation, water vapour and precipitation are influenced by climate change and also contribute to it.

Many media reports on climate extremes provide a bleak outlook, but this is not necessarily the case. Much of the future uncertainty of model outputs is dependant on what goes into the model. In turn this means exactly how we as humans input emissions into the climate system. This was described in 35 scenarios which detail potential futures according to driving factors such as demographic, economic and technological advances, but do not take account of climate initiatives. Prof. Gregory gave an explanation for three of these scenarios that have been tested in great detail (known as A1B, A2 and B1 and range from self-reliance and regional growth with fragmented technological advancements to rapid economic growth followed by the emergence of more efficient clean technologies). Having different future scenarios and therefore a different range of future possibilities creates uncertainty as the 'model' earth reacts differently to anthropogenic inputs into the climate system.

Although models (and scientists) disagree over the exact details of climate change, overall there is agreement between the various models that the climate is changing and this is due to human activity and industrialisation in the past 250 years. Jonathan Gregory stated that there are many aspects of our climate system that we do not understand and therefore cannot model. Over the past 16 years since the first IPCC report we have learnt many things about climate, views have changed and science has progressed. How our climate and weather will change in the future is still impossible to say, but this lecture provided an extremely informative and interesting insight into the complex systems and interactions involved in climate science.

Sally Brown (University of Southampton)

Optical Environmental Sensing V (17th October)

The fifth in the series of Optical Environmental Sensing meetings, organised by the Optical and Environmental Physics Groups of the Institute of Physics, this

year formed one of the technical sessions alongside Photonex, the foremost trade exhibition of the UK's optics community. Seven speakers offered a stimulating set of talks on optical techniques applied to environmental problems, to a fully participatory and appreciative audience.

Proceedings opened with two talks on tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (TDLAS). Philip Martin, of Manchester University, described how many species, including CO, NO₂, and HCl can be measured. A variety of techniques, such as laser cavity enhancement, have been developed to improve the achievable sensitivity. The speaker described approaches for stack and exhaust gas emissions and air breath measurements for health applications. Dackson Masiyano of Cranfield University continued the TDLAS theme, describing the implications of laser speckle for gas absorption measurements.

Three speakers from industry presented at the meeting, making an appropriate link with the exhibition taking place alongside. Perspectives on how new technological developments are advancing the field of optical environmental measurement were well received. One of these, Kim Hampton of LIDAR Technologies Ltd, brought the audience up to date on their efforts to bring LIDAR into the domain of robust and compact instrumentation for the measurement of particulate and gaseous species.

Moira Hilton of Reading University gave a further insight into the potential for collaboration between academia and industry, when she described a Knowledge Transfer Project with Whitfield Solar, to develop a performance tester for solar photovoltaic concentrators. These are arrays of Fresnel lenses, designed to produce a more intense radiation field at the photovoltaic element and are a promising method for reducing the cost or improving the output of a photovoltaic installation.

Perhaps the strongest environmental link of the day came in the talk by Alex Cunningham of the University of Strathclyde. His presentation described phytoplankton fluorescence and touched on the important role of such ocean organisms in climate processes. Efforts to measure the fluorescence from space as an indicator of the health of the organisms were described. The system is complex in optical terms and the measurement challenges are severe, even at sea-level. Although new theoretical and experimental work is revealing problems with the current space hardware, there is an improving understanding of the challenge.

Once again, OES was an interesting and high quality meeting, bringing together academics, users and manufacturers. The sixth in the series of OES meetings is already planned for Edinburgh in 2008.

Peter Hodgson (Corus)

Forthcoming Events

Severe Weather - Origins and Prediction (Organised jointly with the South Central Group)

4th February 2008. Refreshments from 6pm, lecture at 7pm.
University of Southampton (Lecture Theatre B in Building 46 - Physics and Astronomy).

Evening talk by Ross Reynolds, University of Reading

Severe weather occurs on a variety of scales, from the short-lived, small-scale tornado to the much longer lived, 1000 km wide hurricane. Understanding the origin of these two phenomena is one step on the path to successful prediction. Advances in the routine observational network combined with increasing scientific understanding of their birth and evolution has led to significant improvements in their prediction. Tornadoes in both the USA and UK will be discussed as will hurricanes over the North Atlantic.

Refreshments will be served in the Seminar Room from 6pm. Further information may be obtained from Sally Brown (sb20@soton.ac.uk) or Sarah Clark (sc205@soton.ac.uk).

Environmental Physics Group Members' Meeting: First announcement and call for presentations

Wednesday 14th May 2008. Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London W1B 1NT

Building on the success of previous events, the Environmental Physics Group is pleased to announce that the fifth **Members' Meeting** will take place on **Wednesday 14th May 2008** at 76 Portland Place, London.

This year, the day will be divided into two parts, with the first session dedicated to presentations from **early career physicists** (for students and all those who have been in paid employment for less than 10 years) and the second session incorporating **other members'** presentations, including the essay winners and the AGM. Members are invited to contribute oral presentations to the meeting – this is your chance to get involved with the Group.

For early career physicists this presents a unique opportunity to present your coursework, dissertation or research in a relaxed and friendly environment. Early career physicists who previously presented on Members' Day found it an ideal

experience to practice conference presentations and an excellent networking opportunity.

We also welcome presentations from our more experienced members for the afternoon session on any subject relating to environmental physics. The meeting will be an excellent opportunity for the community to get together and discuss the diversity and depth of environmental physics.

As well as there being a variety of talks, the winners of this year's EPG essay competition will be presented with their prizes.

There will be **no charge** to group members attending the meeting. Non-members will also be very welcome to attend (limited number of places available) subject to a registration fee of £10.

The Environmental Physics Group will be allocating a number of *EPG travel bursaries* to this meeting to assist with travel costs. Students are particularly welcome to apply.

If you would like to contribute a presentation, please contact Sally Brown (sb20@soton.ac.uk; other contact details listed at the end of the newsletter), indicating a title or subject, and whether you would be speaking in the morning (early career physicists/students) or afternoon sessions.

Further details of the day will be available in our Spring newsletter.

Physics of Ice: First announcement

10th September 2008, Swansea University

A one-day meeting entitled "Physics of Ice" will be held at Swansea University in conjunction with the British Branch of the International Glaciological Society. Presentations will focus on ice in the global environment. More details to follow, or contact Ian Rutt for further information (i.c.rutt@swansea.ac.uk).

EPG Committee

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Committee Statistics

Starting last year, we have been conducting a survey of the ages of committee members present at our meeting in September. In 2006 the median age was 43, and in 2007 it was 36. Histograms are shown below.

You may have noticed a relationship between the decreasing age of the committee and our attempts to increase the involvement of student and early-career group members. Like all correlations, further investigation is needed to determine if these effects are causally linked.

This newsletter is also available on the web at http://www.iop.org/activity/groups/subject/env/Newsletter/page_7422.html and in larger print sizes.

The contents of this newsletter do not necessarily represent the views or policies of the Institute of Physics, except where explicitly stated.

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